

It is clear from the data that the metal ligand stability constants for the three amino acids under examination follow the order of glycine < iminodiacetic acid and < nitrilotriacetic acid, which is in excellent agreement with the results reported by Schwarzenbach and Biedermann². The increased values of the metal ligand stability constants in the said order may be explained on the basis of the presence of 2 acetic acid groups in IDA and 3 acetic acid groups in NTA, which render these ligands a good deal more reactive towards the generality of the cations, than glycine, as a result of which increased liganding ability is observed from glycine to NTA.

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Micro Determination of Some Azo Dyes with N-bromosaccharin

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AZO compounds constitute an important group of colouring matters known as azo dyes, most of which are used as indicators or in dyeing fibres. There are various methods of analysis of azo compounds¹⁻³, the most recent one⁴ involving bromination with N-bromosuccinimide.

Yet another quick and convenient method has been developed by the present authors for the micro determination of azo dyes using N-bromosaccharin which is a stable and faster brominating and oxidising agent⁵. The sample was allowed to react with excess of N-bromosaccharin in presence of acetic acid for 5-10 minutes at room temperature (25°). After the reaction was over the unconsumed reagent was determined iodometrically. The present method gives highly accurate and reproducible results within an error of 0.5% in most of the cases.

Experimental

A stock solution of each sample was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount of the sample in distilled water or in 10% acetic acid in a 100 ml volumetric flask. All the samples were purified by recrystallisation and their purity was checked by a constant melting point.

An aliquot containing 1-3 mg of the sample was taken in a 100 ml iodine flask. 10 ml 0.02 M solution of N-bromosaccharin (prepared by dissolving 1.3116 g N-bromosaccharin in glacial acetic acid and made upto 250 ml) was added to it. The flask was stoppered and allowed to stand for 5-10 minutes at room temperature (25°) with occasional shaking. After the reaction was over the stopper was washed with 5.0 ml distilled water and then 5.0 ml aqueous potassium iodide solution (10%) was added to it. The contents were shaken thoroughly and kept for a minute. The liberated iodine was titrated with standardised 0.01 M sodium thiosulphate solution using starch (1% aqueous solution) as indicator. A blank experiment was also run under identical conditions using all the reagents except the sample.

Calculation :

$$\text{mg of sample} = \frac{(B - A) \times M \times N}{n \times 2}$$

where, A = ml of sodium thiosulphate solution for sample ; B = ml of sodium thiosulphate solution for

blank; n = moles of N-bromosaccharin equivalent to one mole of sample; M = molecular weight of the sample and N = molarity of sodium thiosulphate solution.

Results and Discussion

It was found that the reaction is complete after 5 minutes in case of methyl red and methyl orange and 10 minutes in case of congo red and chrysoidine, consuming 5, 5, 2 and 2 moles of N-bromosaccharin respectively.

The method may conveniently be applied to any other azo dye having an activated phenyl ring. The estimation of azo-benzene has not been possible even under more rigorous reaction condition. The inertness is probably due to the absence of a ring activating group. It was also observed that the presence of acetic acid was essential for better ionisation of the reagent and a two times excess of the reagent gives accurate results.

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Azine Dyes as Spot Test Reagents†

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THE azine dyes that have been used in spot test analysis are: Neutral Red, Phenosafranin, Methylene Violet, Amethyst Violet, Safranin T, Wool Fast Blue BL and Aposafrafin. Neutral Red has been employed for the detection of nitrite¹ and chlorine², whereas, Safranin T has been utilised for the detection of sugar in urine³, nitrite, nitrous acid⁴, perchlorate⁵ and hypohalites⁶. Safranin T, Phenosafranin, Methylene Violet, Amethyst Violet, Wool Fast Blue BL and Aposafrafin have been used for the detection of palladium(II)⁷ and sulphite, hypophosphite and ascorbic acid⁸. The present paper describes the use of the azine dyes. Neutral Violet, Neutral Red, Azocarmine G, Azocarmine B, Wool Fast Blue GL and Nigrosine (Colour Index Nos. 50030, 50040, 50085, 50090, 50320 and 50420 respectively) as reagents for the

spot test detection of osmium(VIII), arsenic(III) and iodide. The advantages of these reagents are: (1) the tests are very sensitive and (2) the tests are not vitiated by the presence of small amounts of related substances.

Experimental

A standard solution (0.01 M) of arsenic(III) was prepared from E. Merck 'pro analysi' sample of arsenious oxide. Approximately 0.01 M solutions of osmium(VIII) (J and M sample), potassium bromate and potassium iodide (B. D. H. AnalaR samples) were prepared and standardised.

Solutions of the dyes (0.01%) were prepared in deionised water from the following samples:— Neutral Violet: George T. Gurr; Neutral Red: E. Merck; Azocarmine G and Nigrosine: Fluka; Azocarmine B: E. Gurr; Wool Fast Blue GL: Bayer.

The solutions were suitably diluted whenever necessary.

The following procedures are adapted for the detection of the different ions.

Detection of osmium(VIII): One drop (0.05 ml) of the dye solution (0.002% in the case of Neutral Violet and Neutral Red and 0.01% in the case of the other four dyes) is taken in the depression of a spot plate and treated with 2 drops (0.10 ml) of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ sulphuric acid, 2 drops of $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ potassium bromate and 3 drops of $1.25 \times 10^{-2} M$ arsenic(III) solutions [2 drops of $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ arsenic(III) solution while using Azocarmine G, Azocarmine B, Wool Fast Blue GL and Nigrosine]. One drop of the test solution is then added to this mixture and the discharge of the colour of the solution indicates the presence of osmium(VIII).

Detection of arsenic(III): One drop of the dye solution (0.002% in the case of Neutral Violet and Neutral Red and 0.01% in the case of the remaining four dyes), two drops of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ sulphuric acid, two drops of $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ potassium bromate, one drop of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ osmium(VIII) solutions and three drops of deionised water are taken in the depression of a spot plate and mixed well. One drop of the test solution of arsenic(III) is then added and the solution mixed thoroughly. An immediate disappearance of the dye colour indicates the presence of arsenic(III).

Detection of iodide: One drop of 0.002% Neutral Violet or Neutral Red solution (the remaining four dyes are not suitable in this test) is mixed with two drops of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ sulphuric acid, two drops of $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ potassium bromate, one drop of the test (iodide) solution, one drop of deionised water and two drops of $1.25 \times 10^{-2} M$ arsenic(III) solution, in

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